

WALKING FOR MEMORY:

Feminist Resistance, Political Memory and Collective Organization in Argentina

Special Interview with Nora Cortiñas for *La Vida en Violeta*

Video: <https://youtu.be/GAExp6rpjXk?si=0VUwzWb9uCAMZsVD>

TRANSCRIPT TRANSLATION (FIRST PAGE)

Interviewer: Verónica Pereyra Carrillo

Interviewee: Nora Cortiñas, Founding Member of Madres de Plaza de Mayo Línea Fundadora

Verónica Pereyra Carrillo:

How are you, Norita? What an honor it is to have you on *La Vida en Violeta*.

You are part of *Madres de Plaza de Mayo–Línea Fundadora*, and as you know, today's edition of *La Vida en Violeta* is devoted to March 8 and to the ways women organize collectively.

It would be an honor for us to hear your testimony about how the Mothers of Plaza de Mayo organized themselves in Argentina to resist the dictatorship and to search for their disappeared sons and daughters. Could you tell us a little about that experience?

Nora Cortiñas:

We began walking on April 30, 1977, and up to this day we have continued walking in the search for memory, truth and justice.

That is how we have arrived here, after decades of struggle.

Verónica Pereyra Carrillo:

Could you tell us how you first began to organize?

You were also victims of military repression. There were mothers who were disappeared, tortured, and persecuted, and despite all of that, you continued.

Nora Cortiñas:

Yes, exactly.

We always organized ourselves by going out together, by appearing in public, by making ourselves visible.

That collective presence was essential.

Later, alongside our struggle, *Abuelas de Plaza de Mayo* was also created, and many grandchildren have now recovered their identities.

But the struggle continues until every person who was appropriated can know the truth and recover their history.

Verónica Pereyra Carrillo:

The Mothers of Plaza de Mayo are a worldwide example of resistance and women's collective organization.

I must say that I also have a disappeared brother.

At that time, we were living in Salta. My mother would travel to Buenos Aires, and I would accompany her.

I would wait for her in a café while she searched and carried out all the necessary démarches.

For many of us, you were a source of hope.

You continue building memory, truth and justice in order to prevent these practices from ever happening again.

Nora Cortiñas:

And that is why we must continue struggling.

We must never lower our arms.